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CLOUD NETWORK / COMPUTING IMPACT ON INTER-ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST WHICH EFFECTS PERFORMANCE OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: A STUDY OF PAKISTAN'S FIRMS

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Abstract:

This paper analyzes Cloud Computing Impact on Inter-organizational Trust which affects the performance of Supply Chain Management of different Retail, Manufacturing, Financial, IT and Services firms in Karachi, city of Pakistan. A theoretical framework has been constructed that illuminates the role of Inter-organizational Trust in Cloud Computing (CC) and how this can reproduce the superior performance of Supply Chain (SCP) by using arguments of the Social Capital Theory (SCT). A questionnaire was run on 200 individuals having a different position like Senior Manager, Middle Manager and Officer of different Retail, Manufacturing, Financial, IT and Services firms in Karachi, state of Pakistan, and statistically analyze the hypothesis by step by step regression test. The result suggests that Cloud Computing (CC) would be controlled to support Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) to have a strong and significant influence on the association of Supply Chain. To improve complete Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) terms and conditions in organizations managers have to implement Cloud Computing base which creates radical improvement in Supply Chain Performance and the results, therefore, reinforce the across the board to explanation argued by the useful theoretical framework as Social Capital Theory (SCT).

Key Words:

Cloud Computing, Inter-organizational Trust, Supply Chain Performance.

1. Introduction

As the comprehensive group, for the connection of people which actually gives a bundle of knowledge or information compromising the integration of network by the help of common transmission protocols, widely known as Internet. Subsequently the evolution of World Wide Web (www) has also occurred in business re-engineering process. Both have an inner most fight between organizations to estimate or redesign their business processes in order to being competitive by giving competition in this vigorous era of competition. To look over the new technologies in this current hassle of development and adopting it by organizations has become necessary (WU). With the passage of time the Information Communication Technologies (ICT) which comprises on Cloud Computing (CC), Internet of Things (IOT) their leisurely conversion or evolution is a big loss (Atzori *et al.*, 2010) and therefore this current era bringing new possible chances to become apparent for the purpose of constructing applications which satisfactorily merge instantaneous characteristics of physical resources and ultimately replenish the gap between virtual and real world (Distefano *et al.*, 2012). Anyways, in order to absorb Cloud Based services there are the areas of major disturbance like, issue of information security as well as defense in anticipation of non-authorization access (Duncan *et al.*, 2015; Ali *et al.*, 2015), Scarcity into the realization of service providers regarding the privacy potentials (Del alano *et al.*, 2015). Cloud developers and organizations adequate apprehension is required for the application, the lack between these two would not implement it (Autry *et al.*, 2010), technical obstacles (Wang *et al.*, 2010), finance availability in different sectors can forgot with the catering of investments in technologies and competent IT personnel, hence, if financial barriers is the hurdle then it could be so hard to do so (Oliver *et al.*, 2014; Abdollahzadehgar *et al.*, 2013) and lack in confidence (Rahi *et al.*, 2016).

Cloud computing trust is an intricate affair (Tang *et al.*, 2016). To transpire the cloud period trust is one of the most debatable issues (Sindhu and Singh, 2016). Apart from it, Cloud computing is a hot topic for research and educational publication purposes (Salvara and Sundararajan, 2017), well known trust theorists, it is a stick for heading risks that can enhance the technology progressions (Lynnetal *et al.*, 2016). Due to lack in reliability or trust issues bunch of problems are interlinked through the acquisition in services which are cloud base (Rahi *et al.*, 2016). Investigating regarding the performance of Supply Chain in different firms of Karachi, State of Pakistan by adopting Cloud Based Services by keeping in view the major factor effecting performance which is Inter-organizational Trust. This study is highly belongs to it. The most important reason of conducting this investigation is to analyze the

implementation of Cloud Computing technology impact on Organizational Interaction and trust which effect control of SCM and its performance in different firms in Karachi, state of Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

This philosophy is coordinated on Social Capital Theory (SCT). SCT demonstrates benefits which elevate the relationships or bonding between individuals or organizations can bring about. The approaches through which the resources made available in companies through relationships, hence the possession is known as capital. (Lawson *et al.*, 2008) Structural, Social and Cognitive are the factors of Social Capital Theory (SCT) (Ghoshal and Nahapiet, 1998). Altogether goals and allocations or shared visions of supply chain performance provides by the existing resources that suggests by cognitive capital (Krause *et al.*, 2007). Relationships existing formulation is provided by structural capital (Lawson *et al.*, 2008). Interaction give birth to trust and reciprocated exchange on the basis of relationships between the parties is provided by the relational capital (Lawson *et al.*, 2008). It has been cleared that the relationships is the major factor that can increase the momentum of supply chain performance, embracing operations and relational measures is defined in Social Capital Theory (SCT) (Benton and Maloni, 2005). To have a grip on perspective of different firms logistics, manufacturing, retail, services, IT, finance effect on Cloud Computing (CC) impact on Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) which effects the SC efficiency in firms of Pakistan, therefore Social Capital Theory (SCT) is relevant for it.

Abandon information from mobile trickery or desktops provided to a user through remote access offer by cloud computing services and offer considerable guaranty for future expansion (LeRoux and Evans, 2011). Data storing made suitable, fast and net computing services with all way of support pictured as services sent through internet happens by a visible computational paradigm and distribution framework called as cloud computing (Zhong *et al.*, 2010). Acquiesce in internet models through networking and engage virtual resources made easy to send data through cloud computing a service and application, depending technology managed in a distributed network (Rezai *et al.*, 2014). Determine resources and internet delivered services through an application called as cloud computing (hardware and software) hence supply on-demand approach to these resources and services supplied by service suppliers to the instant user by means of Pay-Per-Use services. Service Software (SaaS), Service Platform (PaaS) and Service Infrastructure (IaaS) are all factors of the model of Cloud Network / Computing (CC) (Chen *et al.*, 2016; Lal and Bharadwaj, 2016; Hoberg *et al.*, 2012; Wu 2011; Mell and Grance, 2011).

By organizing time period of organizational threshold of supply network to create value for partners or the members or the stakeholders in a chain of supply chain included consumers, suppliers, shareholders done by integrating business processes is the major concern of supply chain management (Silvesto and Lustrato, 2014). Supply chain information flow is a widespread view of supply chain literature which requires information of supply chain that achieved by holist business processes to have suitable responsiveness (Kembro *et al.*, 2014; William *et al.*, 2013). Supply chain is a different dimension. It is cleared that supply chain is an integration of different organizations or departments to work in collaboration for better performance (Santanu, 2012). Performance measurement requires a proper performance evaluation metrics, procedures, analyze the processes, inspecting continually the important processes (Tian *et al.*, 2003). Evaluation measures are presented in order to achieve the better results (Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2004), for the purpose of measurements all the relevant areas should be inclusive, gain the characteristics of universally to allow the differentiations in several working conditions and on the basis of SCM, Flexibility in Transportation should be calculated (Misra and Sharan, 2014), Order Fulfillment (Mini-Ramirez *et al.*, 2012) and the passing of information (Barrat and Oke, 2004).

A correlated measure consist of association between interacting service to work in a specific time by being secure, dependent, reliable (Pathan and Mohammad, 2005). Trust major supporters are partners in any type of exchange, companies having confidential data and transfer through the help of internet mainly depends on trust between two parties who are users and providers that is why cloud computing is an internet based application (Rotter *et al.*, 2017). In cloud computing trust is a process which is the requirement of all the members to share their information through internet (Goel, 2015; Karamar, 2010), feasible trust requires the parties are universally accept the underlying premise of trust (Xie *et al.*, 2016). Evaluation of trust being an important factor as an magnificent way on cloud computing to warrant service quality (Chiregi and Navimipour, 2017), trust have different classifications, characteristics and applications such as statistics dynamics, Periodic direct, secondary, centralized and constructive delivery, and characteristics as honesty, accuracy, active, secure, adaptable availability and confidentiality, applications as, observe and tracking (Kramar, 2010), in a system different features identify the concept of trust: trust relations, trust domains and management (Goel, 2017). All together found that building reputation among all individual organization is the characteristics of trust to develop an environment related to cloud computing requires all the entities in purpose of maintaining the trust one after the other for creating a web or a network of trust (Goel, 2015).

Cloud computing adoption is based on an important factor which bring on reflects a strong winning factor is trust a relational capability (Garrison *et al.*, 2012). Chiregi and Navimpiour (2017) commence detailed study of trust assessment procedure in cloud based services, Rahl *et al.* (2016) found that the adoption of cloud based services less intense effects, Jabber *et al.* (2016) identified trust model for educational institutions Chahal and Singh (2016) identified a rule for identifying trustworthiness of cloud service provider an export system, Pathan and Mohammad (2015) by using ICT enabled global regulatory body he projected a way Cloud Computing (CC) trust would generate in customers. Goel (2015) examined trusted supply chains by looking over the aggressive value of clouds, Periz *et al.* (2014) gave classifications of the relationships of trust in the circle of cloud circulating, and at last Liu *et al.* (2014) worked on trust building and information transfer relationships based on culture diversity and identify that relationships individuals are more consistent in relationships as compare to dependent one in building the factor of trust. The disagreement between Bapna and Gupt (2011) that growth of interactional information motivated by trust sharing among friends, Ozpolat *et al.* (2016) examined the impact of cloud computing share basis usage and its instantaneous effect on flexibility in flow of peace aid and the concerned information between the beneficiaries who are affected by mishap to cut human deaths. As well as it also identified the efforts related with between Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) and Cloud Computing (CC) for its usage and collaboration. Cloud Computing (CC) was empirically measured through questionnaire filled by 200 respondents from firms of Pakistan. On the basis of the conceptual study, partial least square test used to identify the relationships between variables. Identified how cloud computing is using in firms or provides a positive effects on the collaboration between organizations and suppliers. Collaboration brought positive effect with agility and proved a valid model Rahi *et al.* (2016) study aim to recognize the impact of trust services on Cloud Based by adopting Cloud Computing (CC) in industries of Pakistan. Current learning took Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) as a mandatory influence on the partnership between Cloud computing technology adoption and Quality of the Supply Chain. Framework implicitly or explicitly, leads to achievement of objectives on the Supply Chain Performance by adopting cloud based services.

Ho1: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on Cloud Networking / Computing (CC) in performance of Supply Chain (SCP).

Ho2: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on relationship between Cloud Network / Computing (CC) and Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF).

Ho3: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on relationship between Cloud Network / Computing (CC) and Order Fulfillment (OF).

Ho4: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on relationship between Cloud Network / Computing (CC) and Information Sharing (IS).

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

According to Marczyk, DeMatteo, and Festinger (2005) the two techniques were used for research which is known as qualitative and quantitative. Quantitative research works on the basis of amount or quantity measurement. It is used in the phenomena that can be shown in quantity terms. On the other hand, Qualitative research is related with the qualitative phenomenon, i.e., phenomenon that involves kind or quality. The research which indicates the wider perspective which is based on practice and observation of individual which contribute descriptive data should be known as Qualitative. The research data which is utilized for analyzing variables and clear method for interpret are considered as quantitative (Cavana *et al.*, 2001). This research has developed superior study for determination of high concentration of variable impact on our learning. The research which is easy to interpret in numeral number and their association of variables that's our learning is establishing on quantitative approach (Mugenda, 1991). In this research, quantitative close- ended and structured questionnaire was used and collected numeral data which is more coordinated and arrangement form. Therefore, our research is aligning with quantitative approach method.

3.2 Study Population and Sample

In order to collect first-hand primary data, this study has targeted from different Retail, Manufacturing, Financial, IT and Services firms in Karachi, City of Pakistan to collect data using random sampling technique and quantitative questionnaire. The study targeted to gather 200 total sample responses from the specified target population.

3.3 Research Framework

3.4 Questionnaire and Data Gathering

The units of analysis were selected through questionnaire applying random sampling technique. The sample constitutes of different firms and 88 percent response rate was used for the analysis.

3.5 Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

For both constructs validities and content survey instrument is used in command to ensure that statement represent effectively and properly what it tends to measure, action ensured the validity of the survey. Ahiauzu (2006) and Nunally (1978) recommended that Cronbach's Alpha is used to scientifically analyze the instrument reliability that describe the factors. In Table 1, results of the scale reliability are shown.

Table 1: Shows the reliability measure of the study variables (n=200).

Scale	Dimension	Items	Reliability
CC	Cloud Computing	9	0.887
SCP	Supply Chain Performance	18	0.896
IOT	Inter-organizational Trust	4	0.826

Source: SPSS 22.0 Output (based on 2019 survey data)

The individual item reliability result of the study variables summarizes in Table 1. Significantly, all items are reliable and are used to study the Cloud Computing (CC) impact on Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) which effect the performance of Supply Chain of different firms in Karachi, State of Pakistan. Cloud Computing Service Adoption (0.887) with 9-items measure, Supply Chain Performance (0.896) with 18-item measure and Inter-organizational Trust (0.947) with 4-items measure operationalized extent of the association between the variables.

4 Analysis of Research Question

4.1 Demographic profile of the Respondents

Prospectus	Details	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	39	19.5
	Female	161	80.5
Age	16 – 20	1	0.5
	21 – 30	141	70.5
	30 - 40	52	26
	Above 40	6	3
Position	Middle Manager	71	35.5
	Officer	63	31.5
	Senior Manager	28	14.0
	other	38	19.0

4.2 Analysis of Research Question

In this segment, descriptive relationship presents among the variables Supply Chain Performance (SCP), Inter- organizational Trust (IOT) and Cloud Computing (CC). Descriptive Statistic presents the relationship of research question earlier stated in the study. In table 2, interaction of Cloud Computing (CC), Inter- organizational Trust (IOT) and Supply Chain Performance (SCP) as finding of descriptive present. Difference between the mean significances was investigated by testing among relationship of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT), Cloud Computing (CC), and Supply Chain Performance (SCP). Similar method was used by Nwokah (2006). High and significant mean differences among Cloud Computing (CC), Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) and Performance of Supply Chain (SCP) shown as a result in Table 3, consequently positive link between Inter-organizational Trust (IOT), service adoption of Cloud Computing (CC) and Performance of Supply Chain (SCP) are provided.

Table 2: CC, IOT and SCP (n=200)

	CC	SCP	IOT
Mean	2.078	2.043	1.975
Standard Error of Mean	0.0480	0.0405	0.0479
Standard Deviation	0.6783	0.5731	0.6772
Variance	0.460	0.328	0.459
Skewness	0.578	0.418	0.375
Standard Error of Skewness	0.172	0.172	0.172
Sum	416	409	395

Note: CC = Cloud Computing

IOT = Inter-organizational Trust

SCP = Performance of Supply Chain

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

Ho1: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) doesn't moderating impact of Cloud Networking / Computing (CC) influence in performance of Supply Chain (SCP).

Ho2: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on relationship between Cloud Network / Computing (CC) and Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF).

Ho3: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on relationship between Cloud Network / Computing (CC) and Order Fulfillment (OF).

Ho4: Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) has no effect on relationship between Cloud Network / Computing (CC) and Information Sharing (IS).

Order fulfillment (OF), Information Sharing (IF) and Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF) are the main measures of performance of Supply Chain (SCP), as indicated before. Regression Analysis on each dependent variable by keeping Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) and Cloud Computing (CC) independent Variable and (CC*SCP) variable as interaction, whose outcomes are present in Table 5, 6 and 7.

Decision Rule: If *p-value* is less 0.05 for the interaction term it is rejected Ho, otherwise do not reject Ho.

Table 3: Cloud Computing Impact on Inter-organizational Trust which Effects Performance of Logistic Process Flexibility

(i)	(ii)	(iii)
Variables	Beta Coefficient	p-value
Constant	1.030	0.000
SaaS	0.231	0.000
PaaS	0.037	0.000
IaaS	0.034	0.000
IOT	0.333	0.000
CC*SCP	0.649	0.000
R-square <u>0.572</u>	Adjusted R-square <u>3.577</u>	Probability (F-statistic) <u>0.000</u>

Source: SPSS 22.0 Output (based on 2019 survey data)

On the basis Regression Model, the multiple regression results output generates on the impact of Adoption of Cloud Network / Computing Service (CC) in order to minimize effect of Inter-

organizational Trust (IOT) in Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF). Log in Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF) as a function of linear of Service Platform (PaaS), Service Software (SaaS), Service Infrastructure (IaaS), Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) and the Variable which are Interaction, as stated before. The result of the three Cloud Network / Computing Service Adoption (CC) dimensions (SaaS, PaaS, IaaS) and Inter-organizational (IOT) present the interaction variable.

Table 3, indicates that overall level of significant is high because the probability F-Statistics value is almost Zero (0). The model estimated as a moderate fit because the value of R-squared Adjusted is (3.577), that explain approximately 36% of the total difference in Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF).

In the account of combined model 64% of factors which are remaining are not considered. Mixed signs projected in coefficient i.e., with SaaS (0.231), PaaS (0.037), IaaS (0.034) and IOT (0.333)

having signs association which is positive, as shown in Table 3.

The interaction term has also positive value (0.649) indicated positive coefficient. Moreover, zero (0) probability shows association of all variables. It shows that effects of SaaS, PaaS and IaaS are 1% level significant. The interaction variable and the effects of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) are also significant.

Table 4: Cloud Computing Impact on Inter-organizational Trust which Effects Performance of Order Fulfillment

(i)	(ii)	(iii)
Variables	Beta Coefficient	p-value
Constant	0.713	0.000
SaaS	0.165	0.017
PaaS	0.074	0.208
IaaS	0.142	0.023
IOT	0.382	0.000
CC*SCP	0.579	0.000
R-square <u>0.670</u>	Adjusted R-square <u>4.370</u>	Probability (F-statistic) <u>0.000</u>

Source: SPSS 22.0 Output (based on 2019 survey data)

On the basis Regression Model, the multiple regression results output generates the moderating effects of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) on the influence of Cloud Network / Computing

(CC) in Order Fulfilment (OF) shows in Table 4. As stated before, the Order Fulfillment (OF) log placed as a function of linear of Service Software (SaaS), Service Software (PaaS), Service Infrastructure (IaaS), Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) and the Interaction Variable. The product of the three Cloud Computing (CC) measurements i.e., (SaaS, PaaS, IaaS) and Interorganizational (IOT) present the interaction variable.

Table 4, indicate that overall level of significant is high because probability of F-Statistics value is almost Zero (0). The model estimated as a moderate fit because the value of R squared-Adjusted is (4.370) that explain approximately 44% of the total difference in Order Fulfillment (OF). Hence, in the account of jointly model 56% of factors remaining are not considered.

Mixed signs projected in coefficient i.e., with SaaS (0.165), PaaS (0.074), IaaS (0.142) and IOT (0.382) having signs association which is positive, as shown in Table 4.

The interaction term has also positive value (0.579) indicate positive co-efficient. Moreover, zero (0) probability shows association of all variables. It shows that effects of SaaS, PaaS and IaaS are 1% level significant. The interaction variable and the effects of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) are also significant. The interaction variable and Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) both effects significantly at 1% level. So, suggesting that Cloud Computing (CC) and Order Fulfillment (OF) moderate the relationship with Inter-organizational Trust (IOT).

Table 5: Cloud Computing Impact on Inter-organizational Trust which Effects Performance of Information Sharing

(i)	(ii)	(iii)
Variables	Beta Coefficient	p-value
Constant	0.149	0.171
SaaS	0.032	0.430
PaaS	0.111	0.061
IaaS	0.130	0.039
IOT	0.675	0.000
CC*SCP	0.660	0.000
R-square 0.634	Adjusted R-square 6.260	Probability (F-statistic) 0.000

Source: SPSS 22.0 Output (based on 2019 survey data)

On the basis Regression Model, the multiple regression output generates the moderate effects of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) on the influence of Cloud Network / Computing (CC) in Information Sharing (IS) shows in Table 5. As stated before, the Information Sharing (IS) log placed as a function of linear of Service Software (SaaS), Service Platform (PaaS), Service

Infrastructure (IaaS), Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) and the Interaction Variable. The product of the three Cloud Network / Computing (CC) measurements i.e., (SaaS, PaaS, IaaS) and Inter-organizational (IOT) present the interaction variable.

Table 5, indicate that overall level of significance is high because value of F-Statistics is almost Zero (0). The model estimated as a moderate fit because the value of R squared-Adjusted is (6.260) that explain approximately 63% of the total difference in Order Fulfillment (OF).

In the account of combined model 37% of factors which are remaining are not considered. Mixed signs projected in coefficient i.e., with SaaS (0.032), PaaS (0.111), IaaS (0.130) and IOT (0.675) having signs association which is positive, as shown in Table 5.

The interaction term has also positive value (0.660) indicated positive coefficient. Moreover, zero probability shows association of all variables. It shows that effects of SaaS, PaaS and IaaS are 1% level significant. The interaction variable and the effects of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) are also significant. The interaction variable and Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) both effects significantly at 1% level. So, suggesting that Cloud Computing (CC) and Information Sharing (IS) moderating the relationship with Inter-organizational Trust (IOT).

With positive co-efficient, interaction term is associated with value (0.660). All variables having probability which is low, Shows Cloud Computing (CC) profitability is significant as individual effects. Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) creating significant effect statistically by associating high probability which indicates by coefficient of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT). The value of Inter-organizational Trust (IOT) coefficient is (p-value=0.675) with associated as high probability. Zero (0) probability associated with interaction term (CC*SCP), which shows the relationship between Information Sharing (IS) and Cloud Computing (CC) have highly and positive significant on Inter-organizational Trust (IOT).

Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF) model generally performs on both Information Sharing (IS) model and Order Fulfillment (OF) model to show the result after close examination. Model of Logistics Process (LP) value of Adjusted R Square is 0.572 or 57%, Model of Order Fulfillment (OF) value of Adjusted R-Square is 0.670 and Model of Information Sharing (IS) value of R-Square Adjusted is 0.634 as reported earlier would take as an example. In table 4, Logistics Process Flexibility (LPF) model estimation based hypothesis test was carried, as mentioned in column 3 p-values which are only focused. The value of interaction term in table 5, i.e. 0.0000 which is less than 0.05, show association of p-value (t-statistic) which is link with (CC*SCP). Result shows that null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis supports the finding to identify effects Inter-organizational Trust of Cloud Computing on Supply Chain Performance. The results of Hypothesis testing are shown Table 6.

Table 6: Result of hypothesis testing

Hypothesis (Null)	Accept / Reject
Ho1	Reject
Ho2	Reject
Ho3	Reject
Ho4	Reject

5. Conclusion

The statistical results reveal that Cloud Network / Computing service adoption significant impact on Inter-organizational Trust effects the Supply Chain Performance. The impact of Cloud Network / Computing Service Adoption on Supply Chain Performance remains significantly positive if the Inter-organizational Trust remains the same or constant, hence it shows that Inter-organizational Trust impact Cloud Network / Computing Services. Hence Inter-organizational Trust is a major factor in of relationships between the partners.

This paper concludes a fact also that the respondents working in different firms they actually know the trust level and well understood the inter-organizational trust factor within that company. Goel (2015) put light on attaining less or minimal assets, then members trust the system less. Hence it concluded that when the information transferring in cloud is done by members and they contain the right of possession ultimately their trust level is high.

Other than that trust among the members of Supply Chain is identified by Cao *et al* (2017) transferring of data with respect to the use of cloud network / computing will support in increasing security issues within the partners transferring the data. To sum up, this paper analyzes by using the social capital theories points, the effect of trust of cloud computing on Supply Chain performance, this model lighten that how this framework generate superior level of SC performance. A survey is done to gather data from 200 respondents in different firms of Pakistan. Regression method was used to test the hypothesis. It also concluded that significantly positive. Hence Inter-organizational Trust is a building factor of analyzing supply chain performance by influence of Cloud Computing. Therefore Cloud Computing requires trust as a moderating factor to have a significant trust on supply chain and social capital theory is a framework for it to analyze how performance achieve peak level of superiority.

5.1 Limitation and Suggestion for future research

Different firms of Pakistan have identified a point of specific understanding that the firms should admit the existence of truth about the benefits of cloud computing. The better

performance of supply chain management including (flexibility of logistics & sharing of information's) are the findings of benefits. When the consolidated two events cloud computing & inter organizational trust occurs at the same time they both enhance & strengthen the coordination between supply chain partners. Firms of Pakistan should be ready to create practices of inter organizational trust which have the ability to increase cloud computing services which ultimately make the performance of supply chain better. The whole study put light on firms of Pakistan who acquire high position & are the part of final products. Continually interaction between upstream and downstream companies in different field's conclusion of findings cover here should be widely distributed.

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